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AIRBORNE PARTICULATE MATTER: A POTENTIAL THREAT
TO POLLINATORS

*Il particolato atmosferico: una potenziale minaccia
per la salute degli impollinatori*

Airborne Particulate Matter (PM) is an emerging pollutant characterized by a mixture of chemical components, classified by size which may range from 10 μm (PM₁₀) to 0.1 μm (PM_{0.1}) (BROWN *et al.*, 2003). The potential to elicit the adverse biological effects of PM exposure is strictly linked to the size, chemical composition and morphology of the components. Exposure to airborne PM may occur through inhalation but also ingestion of contaminated food (LOMER *et al.*, 2002). Recent studies on oral exposure of honey bees to PM made of metal oxides demonstrate lethal and sub-lethal health effects (AL NAGGAR *et al.*, 2020; PAPA *et al.*, 2021a).

The honey bee *Apis mellifera* is a well-known bioindicator, able to provide information on environmental pollutants by analysing the traces present in its body and in hive products (SATTA *et al.*, 2012). The honey bee is also an efficient sampler of airborne PM (NEGRI *et al.*, 2015). During the flight and foraging activity, the hairy body of the insect accumulates electrical charges which enhance attraction with airborne dusts. Particles may be characterised morphologically, mineralogically and by size through a Scanning Electron Microscope provided with X-ray spectroscopy (SEM/EDX) (NEGRI *et al.*, 2015; PELLECCCHIA & NEGRI, 2018; CAPITANI *et al.*, 2021; PAPA *et al.*, 2021b). In heavily polluted environments, the dusts may also contaminate honey and pollen (PAPA *et al.*, 2021a, 2021b), thus posing a risk for the health of the honey bee but also of other pollen-feeding insects including key pollinators.

Here we present a case study on the characterization of pollutant PM in

honey and pollen collected from a bee colony living in a highly polluted area of Italy. The area falls inside the Po Valley (Northern Italy), one of the most important industrial and agricultural areas in Europe, characterized by a high population density and a low level of air quality. Previous source apportionment studies indicate that, during the warm season, PM_{10} and $PM_{2.5}$ mainly originate from vehicular traffic and agriculture (MARCAZZAN *et al.*, 2001).

By using the honey bee as an alternative PM sampling method, recent studies by Papa and colleagues (CAPITANI *et al.*, 2021; PAPA *et al.*, 2021b) demonstrated the specific contribution of motor traffic, waste incineration, and agricultural operations to PM_{10} , $PM_{2.5}$, PM_1 and $PM_{0.1}$.

The honey produced by the colony and the pollen grains collected by bees have been investigated for the presence and characterization of PM. SEM/EDX analysis confirmed that the bee products were contaminated by PM from natural and/or anthropogenic sources (Fig.1).

Fig. 1 — (a) A particle made of iron oxides/hydroxides (arrow) on pollen of a Brassicaceae; (b) Corn pollen contaminated by gold particles (bright spots); (c) a multigrain aggregate of quartz on a pollen grain (d) backscattered electron micrographs of vehicle-derived PM contained in honey.

Pollen collected by bees from wild and cultivated plants (e.g., Brassicaceae, dandelion, corn, blackthorn, and alfalfa) showed the presence of PM₁₀ and PM_{2.5}. Among naturally-derived minerals are clays, feldspars, calcite, and quartz, that could be resuspended from the soil by wind or during agricultural operations (e.g., sowing and harvesting). Round-shaped dusts of silicon dioxide and PM made of gold could be originated from incineration activities. Indeed, the spherical morphology is a well-known indicator of high-temperature combustion like that occurring at incinerator plants and bottom ash can be rich in precious metals derived from waste of electrical and electronic equipment. Among anthropogenic PM is also Fe and Fe alloys, that may originate from the wearing of mechanical parts or the braking systems of vehicles, and barite, that is widely used in vehicle tires and brakes (ÖSTERLE *et al.*, 2001; KUKUTSCHOVÁ *et al.*, 2011). Also, an anthropogenic origin for titanium dioxide particles contaminating the pollen is suggested, as synthetic TiO₂ is widely employed as a filler and a whitening agent in plastics, paints, and vehicle components.

Regarding honey, SEM/EDX analyses revealed the presence of PM_{0.1} made of Fe-oxides and barite, and PM₁₀ and PM_{2.5} made of quartz, Fe alloys, TiO₂, and clay minerals.

Since honey and pollen are key elements of the honey bee diet, our work suggests that both managed and wild colonies of *A. mellifera* may be exposed to PM via the oral route, with possible consequences on their health. Similarly, pollen-feeding insects including many important pollinators can be harmed by ingestion of airborne dust. Specific ecotoxicological studies are therefore needed to evaluate the exposure levels of pollinators to pollutant PM and the potential risk for their health.

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